

Solvent Effect on Ion-Dipole Type of Reactions : Acid Hydrolysis of Ethyl Formate in DMSO—Water Medium

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The rate of acid catalysed hydrolysis of ethyl formate has been studied in aqueous DMSO of composition ranging from 0 to 60% of DMSO at temperatures varying from 20° to 40°. The rate is found to increase initially with maxima at about 9 mole percent of DMSO and then decreases on further addition of the organic component. The enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) and entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) have been evaluated using the equation of Wynne Jones and Eyring. The non-linearity of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger with increasing mole % of DMSO are indicative of definite solvation changes taking place in the medium. The variation in free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) values with increasing mole % of DMSO were found to be almost negligible. The variations of the rate constant and the activation parameters have been explained on the basis of solvent-solute interaction, solvation of the transition state and the dielectric behaviour of the medium.

STUDY of the solvent effect of aprotic solvent on the reactions such as hydrolysis of esters and amides have been carried out by a number of workers¹⁻⁵, but the explanations put forward are not quite satisfactory.

According to the theory of Parker⁶, the rate of such reactions in which the transition state passes through large polarisation should be faster in aprotic solvents than in protic solvents. This contention of Parker was subsequently supported by Roberts^{4,7} who studied the alkaline hydrolysis of a large number of esters in DMSO-water mixtures and observed the enhancement of the rate by increasing ratio of aprotic component of the binary solvent mixture. However, this goes against the qualitative prediction of Hughes and Ingold⁸ as well as the theoretical prediction of Laidler and Landskroener⁹. According to them the rate of such reactions should increase with increasing dielectric constant of the medium.

Therefore, in the opinion of the authors more investigations are needed to arrive at a definite conclusion. Primarily with this view and also to find out the activation parameters to study the mechanism of the rate processes, it has been decided to study the rate of hydrolysis of a very simple ester ethyl formate in DMSO-water mixtures which has not been studied so far.

Experimental

Ethyl formate (BDH quality) was distilled. Standard solution of A. R. grade HCl (0.01M) was prepared in solvent mixtures of extrapure DMSO varying from 5-60% in double distilled water. The

above solution was thermostated in a bath controlled within $\pm 0.5^\circ$. After 15 minutes 1 ml of ethyl formate was added to the above thermostated solution. 10 ml aliquot of the reaction mixture at a definite interval of time was removed and quenched in ice-cold water and titrated by standard Baryta solution. Reproducible results were always obtained.

The specific rate constants calculated in various solvent mixtures at temperatures 20°, 25°, 30°, 35° and 40° are shown in Table I. The table also includes the dielectric constant values interpolated from the curve using the data of Wolford².

Results and Discussion

The rate of acid catalysed hydrolysis of ethyl formate in various DMSO-water mixtures at temperatures varying from 20° to 40° has been listed in Table I. The composition of solvent has been varied from 0 to 60% v/v of DMSO.

It is very interesting to note that the rate of hydrolysis of ester increase no doubt with increasing mole percent of DMSO in the beginning as expected on the basis of the theory put forward by Parker⁶ but it comes to a maximum and then the specific rate starts falling. The maximum which is obtained by plotting log k values against solvent composition was found to be 8.82 mole percent of DMSO (corresponding to 27.68% of DMSO by volume) at all the temperatures. The finding supports the contention that both solvent solute interaction and the dielectric effect are imperative and none can be neglected. The inference made by Gelles *et al.*¹⁰ that a solvent solute interaction is the more probable factor influencing the rate, the

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANT OF ACID HYDROLYSIS OF ETHYL FORMATE IN DMSO-WATER MIXTURES AND THE CORRESPONDING DIELECTRIC CONSTANTS

Percentage (v/v) of DMSO	20°C		25°C		30°C		35°C		40°C	
	$k \times 10^4$ min ⁻¹	D								
0%	10.55	80.15	16.17	78.30	24.55	76.33	36.33	74.83	54.17	73.13
5%	10.88	80.08	16.64	78.20	25.59	76.43	37.35	64.73	55.38	73.03
10%	11.39	79.93	17.37	78.05	26.06	76.33	38.79	74.63	57.88	72.93
15%	11.93	79.76	18.05	77.85	27.12	76.17	40.11	74.50	59.41	72.83
20%	12.35	79.60	18.75	77.70	28.07	76.00	41.50	74.30	61.46	72.60
30%	13.04	78.98	19.64	77.10	29.54	75.40	43.31	73.70	64.06	72.00
40%	11.94	78.00	17.82	76.05	26.92	74.40	39.81	72.75	59.23	71.10
50%	10.26	76.40	15.58	74.55	23.50	72.86	35.32	71.25	51.88	69.55
60%	8.22	74.00	12.59	72.30	19.38	70.70	29.17	69.10	43.90	67.50

TABLE 2—CALCULATED VALUES OF ΔH^* IN K cal/mole, ΔG^* IN K cal/mole AND $-\Delta S^*$ IN cal/deg/mole IN DIFFERENT SOLVENT MIXTURES

% of DMSO (v/v)	ΔH^*	20°C		25°C		30°C		35°C		40°C	
		ΔG^*	$-\Delta S^*$								
0%	14.35	23.52	31.30	23.68	31.31	23.83	31.30	24.00	31.33	24.15	31.31
5%	14.30	23.50	31.40	23.66	31.41	23.81	31.40	23.98	31.42	24.13	31.42
10%	14.25	23.47	31.47	23.63	31.48	23.80	31.49	23.96	31.50	24.11	31.48
15%	14.17	23.45	31.67	23.61	31.69	23.77	31.70	23.73	31.71	24.09	31.70
20%	14.08	23.43	31.89	23.59	31.90	23.75	31.91	23.91	31.92	24.07	31.90
30%	13.98	23.40	32.13	23.56	32.16	23.72	32.15	23.89	32.17	24.04	32.15
40%	14.03	23.45	32.07	23.61	31.12	23.78	32.11	23.94	32.11	24.09	32.09
50%	14.24	23.53	31.73	23.70	31.75	23.86	31.76	24.01	31.74	24.17	31.75
60%	14.70	23.66	30.59	23.83	30.62	23.97	30.61	24.13	30.62	24.28	30.60

dielectric constant becoming only a secondary factor, may be correct in certain cases, but it is not a general feature. The variation of rate constant with increasing mole percent of organic co-solvent in our case clearly shows that the factors influencing the rate are of two types. While one type increases the rate the other type hinders its progress and naturally the observed rate will depend on their relative magnitude. Now the possible factor increasing the rate is the solvation changes of reactants and the transition state. Aqueous DMSO medium has been termed as TNAN type of binary mixtures as reported in the various communications¹¹. Intermolecular association of this solvent often occurs in such type of binary mixtures. Packer and Tomlinson¹² have pointed out the breakdown of water-water interaction by adding DMSO as a co-solvent in it. Therefore due to strong tendency of DMSO to break down the water-water interaction to its aqueous binary mixtures, it is quite possible that it may enter into the "structure broken" region of the solvation sheets of the different ionic species. Also DMSO being a dipolar aprotic solvate by ion-dipole type of mechanism, the transition state being large cation is likely to be solvated more than the initial state. This change in solvation will decrease the activation energy (which is apparent from ΔE or ΔH^* values) and thereby increase the rate. This accounts for increase of the rate in beginning. The factor decreasing the rate is quite probably the decrease of bulk dielectric. The increase of DMSO

in the binary solvent mixture decreases the bulk dielectric on account of its low value compared to water. This decrease of dielectric constant may lower the concentration of highly polar transition state and thereby decreases the rate. While the former effect is more predominating in the beginning causing an increase in the rate, the latter effect outweighs the former after 8.82 mole percent causing uniform decrease in the rate.

The activation parameters for the acid catalysed hydrolysis of ethyl formate were calculated using Wynne-Jones and Eyring equation¹³ in the following form :

$$\log \frac{k}{T} = \left(\log \frac{k}{h} + \frac{\Delta S^*}{2.303R} \right) - \frac{\Delta H^*}{2.303RT}$$

From the plot of $\log \frac{k}{T}$ against $\frac{1}{T}$ the values of ΔH^* and ΔS^* were obtained. The values of ΔG^* were then obtained by the thermodynamic relation :

$$\Delta G^* = \Delta H^* - T\Delta S^*$$

It was further observed that the values of E_{exp} obtained by Arrhenius equation was nearly equal to ΔH^* values within the limit of precision. These thermodynamic parameters have been tabulated in Table 2. On perusal of the data in the table, the

continuous decrease in the ΔH^* values in the beginning followed by an uniform increase on addition of DMSO is apparent. Although this small variation may not be taken for the minimum considering the magnitude of errors inherent in the estimation, but the non-linearity in ΔH^* values with increasing mole percent of DMSO is quite clear and is indicative of definite solvation taking place in the medium according to Saville and Hudson¹⁴.

Again it is observed further that there is decrease in ΔS^* also in the region. This means that the conversion of initial state in the transition state is accompanied by entropy decrease which is in conformity with the assumption that the transition state becomes more and more solvated compared to initial state as the mole per cent of DMSO is increased. However, the variation in free energy of activation ΔG^* is considerably small and can be taken as nearly constant. Therefore, in general the variation of rate constants as well as most of the activation parameters is explained on the basis of solvent solute interaction, solvation of the transition state and the dielectric behaviour of the medium.

However, further researches are in progress to apply the results of this investigation in testing the various methods and equations^{6,15-17} suggested from time to time for evaluating the size b^\ddagger of Laidler-Landskroener equation.

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